

OUTDOOR LEARNING TO IMPROVE STUDENT'S SPEAKING SKILL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine whether or not outdoor learning may improve student's speaking skills, and what the students' perspectives are regarding the use of outdoor learning in the context of teaching English. Both qualitative and quantitative methodologies were used in the study.

Keywords: *English language, outdoor learning, outdoor learning activities, speaking skill, teaching and learning*

INTRODUCTION

English is one of the most crucial instruments for forming the skills and characteristics of the younger generation in the age of global integration. The current objective of English lessons is to improve students' speaking abilities. Thus, the achievement of proficiency in speaking is considered the benchmark for foreign language instruction. Learning to talk effectively is very difficult and time consuming. Every instructor must employ efficient teaching techniques to support students in improving their speaking fluency, as evidenced by the realities of English

teaching and learning. Students' learning outcomes are significantly impacted by their learning environment. Therefore, educators ought to design outside activities that provide pupils the chance to converse freely in English in a stimulating classroom setting.

METHODS

Although most language instruction is currently conducted indoors in classrooms, this is not the only option. As a matter of fact, an indoor learning environment is not adequate to fulfill the requirements of the kids. Through the use of outdoor learning, students can practice their language skills in a variety of learning environments. Asama, Anwar, and Muhamad (2016) claim that outdoor learning is synonymous with outdoor education. Similar to this, Vera (2012) defines outdoor learning as a type of study that takes place outside of the classroom and can be set up at the school or somewhere else.

Benefit-wise, Gill (2009) noted that when studying with outdoor learning activities, kids can increase their independence, resistance, and excitement. Moreover, outdoor learning activities improve students' capacity for information exchange and communication with others (Arifani, 2016). They are also believed to maintain the health of the brain (Pearson, 2004). It is consequently well accepted that engaging in outdoor learning activities inspires pupils to learn.

RESULTS

This study examined the impact of outdoor learning on teaching English speaking abilities and students' attitudes toward outdoor learning using both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

DISCUSSION

Regarding advantages, the majority of interviewees recognized the value of outdoor activities in enhancing English language proficiency. First of all, the students

stated that having more opportunity to practice speaking English while collaborating with others while working outside improved their speaking abilities. They realized that participating in outdoor learning activities allowed students to voice their ideas. They also expressed satisfaction with in-person communication and idea sharing with others.

CONCLUSION

Not only may outdoor learning spark students' interest in the subject matter, but it can also foster the growth of their vocabulary, creativity, and self-assurance. Above all, experiential learning activities provide a greater number of chances for students to practice speaking English in authentic contexts. As a result, individuals can pick up new skills and become more proficient speakers of the target language. Even though it can be difficult, there is no denying that outdoor learning has a positive impact on children' learning results, particularly speaking ability.

REFERENCES

1. Asama, C. H, Anwar, C, & Muhamad, R. N. (2016). EFL Learners' Perception toward an Outdoor Learning Program. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*. 4(2). 74-80.
2. Arifani, Y. (2016). The Implementation of Team-Based Discovery Learning to Improve Students' Ability in Writing Research Proposal. *International Education Studies*. 9(2), 111-119.
3. Gill, T, (2009). *No Fear: Growing up in a risk-averse society*, London, Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation.
4. Learson, N. (2004). *The Idiosyncrasies of Out-of-Class Language Learning*. Proceeding of the independent Learning Conference. New Zealand.